

A continuous flow approach for the C–H functionalization of 1,2,3-triazoles in γ -valerolactone as biomass-derived medium

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ARTICLE

A continuous flow approach for the C–H functionalization of 1,2,3-triazoles in γ -valerolactone as biomass-derived medium

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Herein we report an efficient procedure for the C–H functionalization of 1,2,3-triazoles in continuous flow regime applied to a variety of functionalities and to the inter- or intramolecular versions of the process. The continuous-flow protocol is based on the use of a heterogeneous catalyst (Pd/C), a soluble organic base and GVL as reaction medium. Flow conditions allow an optimal recovery/reuse and durability of the catalyst that combined with the simple purification of the products and the recovery of the reaction medium, make the proposed protocol operationally simple and very efficient in terms of waste minimization as proven by low metal leaching and low associated E-factor.

Introduction

The 1,2,3-triazole moiety is widely represented in pharmaceutical compounds as well as in synthetic materials.¹ Therefore, it is not surprising that there is a great interest for the development of scalable, safe and effective synthetic protocols that would efficiently allow to access fully and diversely decorated 1,2,3-triazoles. Heterocyclic systems fused with a triazole ring are possibly even more interesting, as they find application in different fields.² 1,2,3-triazolobenzoheterocycles represent a notable example, with their increasing applications in drug discovery and chemical biology.³

Regioselective syntheses of fully decorated 1,2,3-triazoles has been made possible by the definition of effective protocols for the azide-alkyne cycloaddition (AAC) reaction, or by using halogenated or metalated alkynes.⁴ Extensive optimization has been done and single regioisomers can be accessed by carefully choosing the catalyst and the reaction conditions.⁵ Alternatively, efficient methodologies have been also developed by exploiting the consecutive AAC reaction of terminal alkynes and the direct C–H bond functionalization on the pre-formed 1,4-disubstituted triazoles.⁶

The great advancements of the last decade in C–H activation technologies led to the definition of some of the

most powerful tools for the selective construction of C–C bonds.⁷ General approaches to metal-catalysed direct arylations via C–H bond cleavage are generally based on the use of homogeneous metal catalysts and often of hazardous organic solvents, which makes the available protocols relatively unappealing from the sustainability point of view. Additionally, large amounts of waste are often produced to eliminate the high metal content from the products, in order to fulfil the requested level of purity for the targeted application.

Our research program aims at developing innovative C–H functionalization methodologies⁸ and defining environmentally and chemically efficient synthetic protocols to access highly valuable materials while minimizing the waste production.⁹ To this end, in recent years we made extensive use of safer media¹⁰ and heterogeneous catalytic systems,¹¹ often combining these approaches using flow conditions.

Figure 1. Features of current work.

Solvents used as reaction media are responsible for producing the largest part of the waste generated in chemical productions.¹² Therefore, the choice of a particular reaction

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medium plays a pivotal role in the search for environmentally-sustainable chemical methodologies.¹³

Recently, researchers' attention has directed towards the use of more sustainable substitutes to replace fossil derived and toxic solvents.¹⁴ In this contest, we have been pioneering the use of γ -valerolactone (GVL), a chemical typically produced by hydrogenation of lignocellulosic biomass-derived levulinic acid¹⁵ and possessing very intriguing physical-chemical properties, to replace toxic polar aprotic solvents such as DMF, DMAc and NMP in metal catalysed cross-coupling and C–H functionalization reactions.¹⁶

We have proven that GVL is not only a safer, non-toxic and more sustainable chemical, but it also features peculiar chemical behaviors, such as the tendency to minimize metal leaching from a heterogeneous catalyst, thus improving the catalyst-recyclability.¹⁶

In this context, we have also proven that flow chemistry can lead to additional benefits in terms of waste minimization and preservation of the catalyst stability and longevity.^{11,16a}

In this contribution we report our results on the definition of an effective, waste minimized and safe protocol for the large scale continuous-flow preparation of fully decorated 1,2,3-triazoles, including benzochromeno- and indolino-fused triazoles, based on inter- or intramolecular C–H functionalization reactions.

We have developed our protocol by exploiting GVL as reaction medium and by setting custom-made flow reactors, packed with commercially available and cheap heterogeneous Pd/C catalyst. We have also optimized our conditions in order to set the recovery and reuse of the metal catalyst, minimizing its leaching into the product, and of the reaction medium, in order to minimize dramatically the waste production.

Results and Discussion

We started our investigation by testing different bases in the representative C–H activation/intramolecular cyclization of substrate **1a** promoted by Pd/C in GVL (Table 1). Commonly used potassium trifluoroacetate (KTFA) and potassium carbonate gave good results in terms of reactivity (Table 1, entries 1 and 2), but their solubility in GVL is very limited. Moreover, the stoichiometry of the process leads to the formation of the corresponding highly insoluble potassium iodide. This is an important issue in the design of flow conditions, since insoluble species would result in undesired clogging of the system. Therefore, we shifted our attention to tetrabutylammonium acetate (TBAAc), since alkylammonium bases certainly feature higher solubility in organic environments.^{8b} TBAAc has already proved to be effective as promoter in C–H activation processes.¹⁷ Under the selected conditions, tetrabutylammonium acetate is effective in the cyclization of **1a** giving slightly higher yield (Table 1, entry 3) compared to KTFA and K₂CO₃, with the additional advantage of a high solubility in GVL.

As expected, moving from iodinated **1a** to the equivalent brominated substrate **3aBr**, lower reactivity was observed and the use of K₂CO₃, KTFA or TBAAc resulted in 67%, 69% and 43% isolated yield of **4a**, respectively (Table 2, entries 1-3).

Furthermore, in this reaction we started to observe the formation of dehalogenated product **5a**. These unsatisfactory results prompted us to test the use of other bases, in otherwise optimal reaction conditions, namely, 5 mol % of Pd/C in the presence of 30 mol % of pivalic acid in 0.5M GVL at 120 °C (Table 2).

Table 1. Comparison of bases in the cyclization of **1a**.^a

Entry	Base	C (%) ^b	Yield (%) ^c
1	KTFA	89	82
2	K ₂ CO ₃	90	85
3	TBAAc	94	87

^a Reaction conditions: **1a** (1 eq, 0.5 mmol), Pd/C (5 mol %, 0.025 mmol), MesCO₂H (30 mol %, 0.15 mmol), base (2 eq, 1 mmol), GVL (1 mL). ^b Conversion to **2a**, measured by GC analyses using samples of pure compounds as reference. ^c Isolated yield of the pure product.

Table 2. Comparison of bases in the cyclization of **3aBr**.^a

Entry	Base	C (%) ^b	4a/5a	Yield (%) ^c
1	KTFA	85	88/12	67
2	K ₂ CO ₃	92	87/13	69
3	TBAAc	62	89/11	43
4	DABCO	14	14/86	N.D.
5	DBU	48	0/100	-
6	BEMP	76	55/45	38
7	Me-TBD	90	78/12	64
8	TBAAc:TBAI (1:0.6)	97	100/0	87

^a Reaction conditions: **3aBr** (1 eq, 0.5 mmol), Pd/C (5 mol %, 0.025 mmol), MesCO₂H (30 mol %, 0.15 mmol), base (2 eq, 1 mmol), GVL (1 mL). ^b Conversion to products, measured by GC analyses using samples of pure compounds as reference. ^c Isolated yield of the pure product **4a**.

Using bicyclic nitrogen containing bases as DBU or DABCO little or no conversion to **4a** was observed, with the main formation of dehalogenated **5a** (Table 2, entries 4 and 5). Slightly better results were obtained using BEMP and Me-TBD (Table 2, entries 6 and 7, respectively), but still yields were not

satisfactory. A very good result was then obtained by using a combination of TBAAC and tetrabutylammonium iodide (TBAI) in a 1:0.6 ratio (2 and 1.2 equivalents, respectively, relative to substrate **3a**), achieving a conversion to the desired product **4a** of 97%, with an isolated yield of 87% (Table 2, entry 8). It is noteworthy that under these conditions no formation of **5a** was observed.

Before moving towards the definition of the flow reactor system, we also studied the recovery and reuse of the heterogeneous catalyst. Using the optimized conditions, the palladium leaching was quantified in each reaction run to evaluate possible durability of the catalyst (Table 3). We consistently observed a negligible leaching of palladium species in the reaction mixture. The good recyclability of the catalyst was also confirmed by the constantly good product yields obtained in five consecutive reaction runs (Table 3).

Table 3. Catalyst reuse in the cyclization of **1a**.^a

	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3	Run 4	Run 5
Leaching (ppm)	2.1	1.8	2.3	1.4	1.8
Yield	87 %	87 %	85 %	85 %	83 %

^a Conversion of **1a** consistently above 95%. Reaction conditions: Pd/C (5 mol %), MesCO₂H (30 mol %), TBAAC (2 eq), GVL (0.5M).

Table 4. Optimization of flow conditions for the cyclization of **1a**.^a

Entry	Flow rate (mL/min)	Residence time (min)	C (%) ^b
1	1.0	20	65
2	0.75	30	83
3	0.5	40	93
4	0.25	80	100 ^c
5	0.1	100	100 ^c

^a Reaction conditions: Pd/C (packed in coil flow reactor), MesCO₂H (30 mol %), TBAAC (2 eq), GVL (0.15M). ^b Conversion of **1a** to the corresponding **2a**, the remaining material was **1a**, measured by GC analyses using samples of pure compounds as reference. ^c 87% isolated yield of the pure product.

Encouraged by these results, a customized 2m coil reactor packed with 2 grams of Pd/C catalyst dispersed in glass beads was set in order to investigate the most adequate residence time. The results, reported in Table 4, show that in our flow reactor conversion is complete in 80 min of residence time. Shorter residence time led to a mixture of product **2a** with unreacted starting material **1a**. In the case of longer residence time (100 min), conversion was complete with almost identical results in terms of isolated yield of the pure product (87%) but

in the reaction mixture traces of dehalogenated starting material (compound **5a**) was also detected, suggesting that 100 min residence time is too long. The conditions adopted ensure homogenous conditions and no clogging of the system was experienced.

Scheme 2. Scope of isoindoline-fused triazoles **4a-g**. Data reported refer to the isolated yield of the pure product. Reaction conditions: Pd/C (packed in a coil flow reactor), MesCO₂H (30 mol %), TBAAC (2 eq), GVL (0.15M). ^a A combination of TBAAC:TBAI (1:0.6) was used.

Using the same coil reactor different substrates were reacted under the tested conditions. Our optimized flow reaction conditions proved to be effective for a variety of iodide and bromide substrates (**1a-d** and **1aBr-1dBr**) leading to the formation of different dihydrochromeno-fused triazoles (Scheme 1) in very good yields.

Similarly, several isoindoline-fused triazoles were additionally prepared with highly satisfactory yields, ranging from 82% to 93%. (Scheme 2). It is noteworthy that substrate **3g** was also compatible with the reaction conditions without leading to the dehalogenated product, and therefore opening the possibility for a late stage functionalization of product **4g** (Scheme 2).

We also tested our reactor and flow conditions in the intermolecular C–H activation process leading to the continuous-flow synthesis of fully decorated 1,4,5-trisubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles. The results are summarized in Scheme 3. Also for this intermolecular process, optimal results were obtained using TBAAc as base in combination (for bromide **6b**) or not with TBAI. In all the cases very good yields for the representative fully decorated triazoles **7a,b** were accomplished (Scheme 3).

To evaluate the durability of our catalytic system we have also measured the amounts of palladium species leached in the solvent passing through the packed coil reactor and it is worth-noting that the amount of leached palladium is constantly low with an average value of ca. 0.3 ppm. This result is very valuable, since it means that the purification of the product from metal residues is easier and also that the catalyst is very stable when packed in the flow reactor and when operating under flow conditions. In fact, this conclusion is also supported by the experimental evidence given by the continuous operation of our system with no reduction in efficiency, change in metal leaching, or in product formation after more than 100 mmol, yield being constantly 87%. In flow conditions, loss of palladium measured as leached palladium in solution, represents 0.0015% of the total palladium used per 1 mmol of substrate processed, while under batch conditions this value is 0.16% per mmol processed (see ESI). These data confirm the efficiency of the flow approach in preserving the efficiency of a solid catalyst as it remains packed into the reactor.

Scheme 3. Scope of intermolecular C–H activation in flow. Data reported refer to the isolated yield of the pure product. Reaction conditions: **6a** or **6b** (3 eq), Pd/C (packed in coil flow reactor), MesCO₂H (30 mol %), TBAAc (2 eq), GVL (0.15M).

Finally, in order to define a truly waste-minimized protocol for the synthesis of fully decorated 1,2,3-triazoles, we have also optimized the recovery of GVL by distilling the solvent from the reaction mixture coming out of the flow reactor. At reduced pressure (0.3 mbar) and 150–170 °C temperature, using a Kugelrohr apparatus, GVL was recovered almost quantitatively (ca. 95%). Its purity was confirmed by ¹H- and ¹³C-NMR analyses. The recovered solvent was re-used in subsequent reaction runs without further purification.

Isolation of the pure product was conducted on the oily residue coming from the distillation of GVL, by re-crystallization from acetone/water (1:20) (see ESI). It is noteworthy that the entire substrate scope was performed using the same coil reactor packed with Pd/C (10 % w/w loading) (see ESI) and also with almost the same GVL recovered by distillation.

The use of a soluble organic base allowed performing the reaction in operationally simple flow conditions and in addition led to a considerable waste reduction compared to similar methodologies employing inorganic bases. In fact, the latter inevitably require the separation of the solids from the reaction mixture using classic filtration techniques and an additional aqueous washing of the solid catalyst to clean it from the inorganic salts formed. We calculated for our continuous flow protocol an E-factor as low as 24 (see ESI), a result that also confirms that the flow approach combined with heterogeneous catalysis can be very effective for improving the greenness of a process by minimizing waste production and make the synthetic procedure operationally simpler.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in this contribution we have reported a very chemically efficient and waste-minimized procedure for the C–H functionalization of 1,2,3-triazoles in continuous flow regime. The utility of the protocol is also confirmed by its applicability to a variety of functionalities and also to the inter- and intramolecular versions of the process.

The use of the heterogeneous catalyst (Pd/C) in combination with a soluble organic base and GVL as reaction medium, allowed obtaining the desired products in excellent yields and good hourly productivity. The recovery and reuse of the reaction medium and the durability of the catalyst make our protocol also very efficient in terms of waste minimization as proven by the low associated E-factor.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

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A continuous flow approach for the C–H functionalization of 1,2,3-triazoles in γ -valerolactone as biomass-derived medium

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Answers to Referees

Referee: 1

Comments to the Author

I have an issue with the title. “.....as biomass derived medium”. On introduction the authors say that “.....GVL a chemical TYPICALLY produced frombiomass.....”. Can the authors clearly state if the solvent THEY USED was from biomass or commercial material which may we'll have been chemically manufactured. To state biomass derived in the title of this is not guarantee is serious.

Answer:

The GVL used in the current study was produced from biomass using the procedure reported by Cravotto and coworkers (Molecules 2016, 21, 413). However, unless one believes that chemicals deriving from different sources have different properties, GVL deriving from other sources can in principle also be used. The important point is that GVL can be produced from biomass (and indeed biomass-derived GVL is already commercially available) and thus can be associated to a reduced carbon footprint. Here we prove that this reaction can be conducted in GVL, therefore with a limited consumption of non-renewable resources.

I have also serious concerns about the statement that “ solvents used as reaction media are responsible for producing largest part of waste”. For example in an example in SI where 400 ml of GVL was used 420 ml of ethyl acreege and hexane then used in purification. Ok sometimes necessary but don't make over the to comments.....

Answer:

The sentence is in the introduction and it is not specifically related to our protocol, but more in general, to chemical production.

We thank the reviewer for pointing this out and we have further added citations to works supporting the statement, selected among those generally accepted by the chemical community.

After basic reaction optimization in batch the authors replicate reaction in flow. In introduction ter6 discuss that reaction safer in flow.....regarding*their reaction how is it safer.?

Answer:

In the current manuscript we actually did not specifically focused on the safety of the reported procedure in flow and in comparison to batch.

However, as the reviewer carefully pointed this out, it should be considered that reactions conducted in flow conditions are inherently safer than the corresponding reactions conducted in batch, thanks to the fact that in a flow reactor a limited amount of the reagents (dead volume of the reactor) are exposed to the catalyst at any given time. Conversely, in batch conditions the whole amount of reagents and catalyst are in the presence of each other in the same reactor at all times, thus increasing the possibilities of undesired release of energy on a much larger scale.

Moreover, our reaction conditions are safer compared to previously reported protocols conducted in conventional solvents due to the low toxicity of GVL.

I appreciate reaction shorter, but that undoubtedly because more catalyst. If more catalyst used in batch you could reduce reaction time. So what are the advantages?

Answer:

We would like to thank the reviewer for giving us a chance to clarify the advantages of the reported procedure, which were probably not clear enough.

In order to further clarify the advantages of the flow procedure over batch we also included in the revised ESI an additional experiment aiming at replicating flow conditions but in batch (i.e. a batch reaction with the catalyst/reactant ratio experienced in the flow reactor).

While conducting the reaction in these conditions allow for obtaining similar reaction time as observed in flow, as expected from the much higher catalyst loading, the use of flow conditions still has several advantages:

1) The catalyst is more stable when packed in a flow reactor than when used in batch, as evidenced by a lower leaching of palladium in solution. The higher stability of a heterogeneous catalyst packed in a flow reactor compared to the same catalyst used in batch is not novel, as related examples have been published by us and other research groups. The reduced amount of leached palladium also reflects in an easier purification of the reaction products. The leaching values for flow and batch procedures were already reported in the manuscript. Now we also included in the ESI the value of palladium concentration for the reaction performed in batch using the same catalyst/substrate ratio as in flow conditions (2.74 ppm).

2) The use of flow conditions simplifies the work-up procedure, compared to conducting the reaction in batch on the same amount of product. In fact, when performing the reaction in flow time-consuming and waste-generating washing of the catalyst are unnecessary.

3) Catalyst durability and simplified work-up procedure eventually result in reduced waste-generation, as evidenced by the calculated E-factors. The calculation of E-factor for the batch procedure using the same catalyst/substrate ratio as in flow conditions is now reported in the ESI (64). These new results show that the flow protocol is associated to lower waste-generation compared to batch procedures.

Major clarification to justify if this really is greener.

Answer:

We believe that explanations given above clarify the green feature of the protocol. Many thanks to the reviewer who allowed to improve the manuscript the detailed and specify more efficiently the benefit of the protocol.

Referee: 2

Comments to the Author

Many efficient methodologies including intermolecular and intramolecular have been developed to prepare fully decorated 1,2,3-triazoles by exploiting both the direct C–H bond functionalization on the pre-formed 1,4-disubstituted triazoles and the one-pot CuAAC reaction of terminal alkynes and azides. In this manuscript, the authors reported a procedure for the C–H functionalization of 1,2,3-triazoles in continuous flow regime applied to a variety of functionalities and to the inter- or intramolecular versions of the process. In terms of synthetic methodology, there is only very little novelty in this manuscript. Thus, this manuscript is not recommended to be published in Green Chemistry, although it provides an important greener process.

Answer:

We agree with this reviewer about the availability of procedures for the C–H functionalization of 1,2,3-triazoles. However, in the present report we explicitly focused our attention on the development of a greener protocol for this synthetically important process.

Through a careful optimization of reaction conditions, particularly base, stoichiometry and reaction time, we could maximize the product yield while reducing reaction time and the formation of undesired dehalogenation products. It is important to consider that the reaction conditions reported in the literature cannot be applied to flow conditions. Eventually, the use of our optimized reaction conditions in flow allowed a significant reduction of the waste generated, as evidenced by the calculated E-factors. Thus, we also agree with the reviewer that our procedure represents “an important greener process”. However, we believe that Green Chemistry represents the ideal medium for reporting truly greener protocols for synthetically relevant procedures.

Referee: 3**Comments to the Author**

The manuscript presented by Prof. Vaccaro is very elegant and describes the C-H functionalization of 1,2,3-triazoles using γ -valerolactone as reaction medium. Different aspects of the reaction were explored, such as the reuse of the catalyst with excellent yields after 5 times of use, the use of different halides (Br, I). Various heterocyclic rings were produced with excellent yields with short reaction times. The manuscript is clear and the characterization of the obtained compounds is in agreement with the spectroscopic data.

ELECTRONIC SUPPORTING INFORMATION**A continuous flow approach for the C–H functionalization of 1,2,3-triazoles in γ -valerolactone as biomass-derived medium**

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Page	ESI 25–50	Copies of the ¹ H and ¹³ C NMR spectra

General Information

Unless otherwise stated, all solvents and reagents were used as obtained from commercial sources without further purification. GC analyses were performed using a Hewlett-Packard HP 5890A equipped with a capillary column DB-35MS (30 m, 0.53 mm) and a FID detector. GC-EIMS analyses were carried out using a Hewlett-Packard HP 6890N Network GC system/5975 MassSelective Detector equipped with an electron impact ionizer at 70 eV. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-ADVANCE 400 MHz (^1H at 400 MHz and ^{13}C at 100.6 MHz). The deuterated solvent used was CDCl_3 . Elemental Analyses were conducted on a Fisons EA1108CHN. Melting points were measured on a Büchi 510.

General larger scale procedures and E-factor calculations

General flow procedure using packed Pd/C reactor and organic TBAAc as base

(amounts and calculation for representative 100 mmol scale)

Main features:

- solvent recovery (90 %)
- catalyst safely packed into the reactor
- product isolation by re-crystallization

A premixed mixture of **1a** (100 mmol, 0.041 Kg), TBAAc (200 mmol, 0.060 Kg) and MesCO_2H (30 mol %, 30 mmol, 0.0050 Kg) in GVL (660 mL, 0.15M, 0.66 Kg) was charged into a glass column functioning as a reservoir. The equipment was connected, by using the appropriate valves, to a pump and installed into a box thermostated at 120 °C. The reaction mixture was continuously pumped (flow rate: 0.25 mL·min⁻¹; residence time: 80 min) through the catalyst column and the reaction was monitored by GC. Product was collected in fractions and palladium content of the GVL solution was periodically measured by MP-AES analysis. GVL was distilled from the reaction mixture and 0.594 Kg of GVL (90 % of the initial amount) was recovered as pure compound (confirmed by $^1\text{H-NMR}$). Resulting oil was dissolved in acetone (40 mL, 0.031 Kg), and water (400 mL, 0.4 Kg) was added to precipitate pale brown crystals. Filtration and in vacuo drying gave pure compound (87 mmol, 0.024 Kg, 87 %).

E-factor (100 mmol scale) = $[(0.041_{(\text{substrates})} + 0.060_{(\text{TBAAc})} + 0.0050_{(\text{MesCO}_2\text{H})} + 0.66_{(\text{GVL})} + 0.4_{(\text{water})} + 0.031_{(\text{acetone})}) - (0.594_{(\text{recovered GVL})} + 0.0242_{(\text{isolated product})})] / 0.0242_{(\text{isolated product})} = \underline{\underline{23.9}}$.

Optimized larger scale batch procedure based on our literature protocol using Pd/C as catalyst and KTFA as base (100 mmol scale)

Main features:

- solvent recovery (90 %)
- product isolation by re-crystallization
- optimized amount of water used for washing the catalyst from inorganic salts

Pd/C (0.0054 Kg, 5.0 mol %, 5 mmol), MesCO₂H (0.005 Kg, 30 mol %, 30 mmol), KTFA (0.044 Kg, 300 mmol), substrate (0.0294 Kg, 100 mmol) in GVL (400 mL, 0.42 Kg) was charged into a round bottom flask equipped with magnetic stirring bar and reacted under N₂ for 16 h at 150 °C. After cooling to ambient temperature, the reaction mixture was filtered to separate the catalyst. The catalyst was washed with GVL (200 mL, 0.2 Kg) in order to extract residual product from the catalyst, followed by water (0.4 L, 0.4 Kg), and EtOH (0.2 L, 0.1596 Kg) to wash the catalyst from salts. To the remaining residue, EtOH (0.4 L, 0.318 Kg) was added and the mixture was treated with ultrasound in a sonication bath for 3 h. The solvent was removed after filtration and the residual Pd/C was dried in vacuum at 60 °C overnight. The recovered material was used for the subsequent run (99 % of the total mass of the catalyst was recovered, 0.0053 Kg). The GVL solution containing the products of reaction was distilled (90 % of the total mass of solvent was recovered as pure, 0.558 Kg). Resulting oil was dissolved in ethyl acetate (20 mL, 0.018 Kg), and hexane (0.4 L, 0.26 Kg) was added to precipitate pale brown crystals. Filtration and drying of the solid under vacuum afforded the pure product 3-*n*-Butyl-8*H*-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-*a*]isoindole (0.016 kg, 75 %).

$$\text{E-factor (100 mmol scale)} = [(0.0294_{(\text{triazole})} + 0.0054_{(\text{Pd/C})} + 0.0050_{(\text{MesCO}_2\text{H})} + 0.0442_{(\text{KTFA})} + 0.62_{(\text{GVL})} + 0.4_{(\text{water})} + 0.4776_{(\text{EtOH})} + 0.018_{(\text{EtOAc})} + 0.26_{(\text{hexane})}) - (0.0053_{(\text{recovered Pd/C})} + 0.558_{(\text{recovered GVL})} + 0.016_{(\text{isolated product})})] / 0.016_{(\text{isolated product})} = \mathbf{80}$$

Experiment replicating flow conditions in batch

In order to analyze the differences between flow and batch conditions, we performed a batch reaction using the same catalyst/reactants ratio present at any time in the flow reactor. Therefore, substrate **1a** (1.2 mmol, 0.48 g), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 0.72 g), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL, 7.73 g) and MesCO₂H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 0.06 g), were consecutively added in vial followed by Pd/C (1.88 mmol, 2g). The reaction mixture was stirred at 120 °C and periodically analyzed by GC analysis. After 80 min conversion to product was complete. The reaction mixture was cooled to ambient temperature, and filtered to separate the catalyst. The catalyst was washed first with GVL (12 mL, 12.06 g), in order to extract residual product and TBAAc, followed by EtOH (15 mL, 11.83 g), to wash the catalyst from GVL. Residual Pd/C was dried in vacuum at 60 °C overnight. The recovered material was used for the subsequent reaction run (97 % of the total mass of the catalyst was recovered, 1.94 g). The GVL solution containing the products of reaction was distilled (90 % of the total mass of solvent was recovered as pure, 54.27 g). Resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone (0.4 g) and 5 mL of cold water (5 g) was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (0.285 g, 85 % yield).

$$\text{E-factor:} = [(0.48_{(\text{substrates})} + 0.72_{(\text{TBAAc})} + 0.06_{(\text{MesCO}_2\text{H})} + 7.73_{(\text{GVL})} + 12.06_{(\text{GVL wash})} + 11.83_{(\text{EtOH wash})} + 0.4_{(\text{acetone})} + 5_{(\text{water})}) - (17.81_{(\text{recovered GVL})} + 1.94_{(\text{recovered catalyst})} + 0.285_{(\text{isolated product})})] / 0.285_{(\text{isolated product})} = \mathbf{64}$$

Concentration of Pd measured by MP-AES analysis in the GVL solution: **2.74 ppm**

Calculation of E-factors for Representative Literature Procedures

The procedures and *E*-factor calculations described below are representative. In the evaluation of the results obtained, it should be considered that these procedures have not been specifically optimized for larger scale and/or waste minimization protocols.

Reference	General Procedure	E-factor calculation
<p><i>Org. Lett.</i>, 2010, 12, 2056–2059</p> <p>Lutz Ackermann, Rajkumar Jeyachandran, Harish K. Potukuchi, Petr Novák and Lea Büttner</p>	<p>Pd(OAc)₂ (11.2 mg, 0.05 mmol, 5.0 mol %), Cu(OAc)₂·H₂O (200 mg, 1.00 mmol), PivOH (500 mg, 4.90 mmol) and triazole 1a (287 mg, 1.00 mmol) in dry toluene (3 mL) were stirred in a sealed tube at 140 °C for 20 h. H₂O (50 mL) was added at ambient temperature, and the resulting mixture was extracted with EtOAc (3 x 50 mL). The combined organic layers were washed with sat. aq. NH₄Cl (50 mL), H₂O (50 mL) and brine (50 mL), dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated in vacuo. The remaining residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (n-hexane/EtOAc = 10/1 → 5/1) to yield 2a (274 mg, 96%) as a yellow oil.</p>	<p>Calculation of <i>E</i>-factor (1 mmol scale)</p> <p>(0.96 mmol, yield 96%)=[(0.287(triazole) + 0.011(Pd(OAc)₂) + 0.200(Cu(OAc)₂) + 0.500(PivOH) + 2.61 (toluene, density = 0.87 g/mL) + 53 (NH₄Cl density = 1.06 g/mL) + 135 (EtOAc density = 0.902 g/mL) + 150 (water))] – [(0.274 (isolated product))] / 0.274 (isolated product) = 1245</p> <p>(column chromatography was not considered in <i>E</i>-factor calculation)</p>
<p><i>RSC Adv.</i>, 2013, 3, 2710–2719</p> <p>Chung-Yu Chen, Cheng-Hao Yang, Wan-Ping Hu, Jaya Kishore Vandavasi, Mei-Ing Chunga and Jeh-Jeng Wang</p>	<p>The starting material (4-((2-iodophenoxy)methyl)-1-phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazole derivatives) (1.0 mmol, 377 mg) was dissolved in the dry N,N-dimethylformamide (10 mL, 9.4 g), followed by treating with tetrabutylammonium iodide (TBAI, 3.0 mmol 967 mg), after which Pd(OAc)₂ 5 mol% (5 mg) was added to the reaction and stirred for 6–12 h at 100 C. Progress was monitored by TLC to confirm the starting materials had been consumed and then the reaction mixture was poured out on ice cooled water and extracted with ethyl acetate (2 x 200 mL 360 g) and the combined organic layers were washed with water (2 x 200 mL 400 g), brine (1 x 200 mL 238 g), dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. Crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel 0.040–0.633 mm, Ethyl acetate: Hexane = 1:3) to obtain a white solid 209.3 mg (84%)</p>	<p>Calculation of <i>E</i>-factor (1 mmol scale)</p> <p>(0.84 mmol, yield 84%)=[(0.377(triazole) + 0.005(Pd(OAc)₂) + 0.967(TBAI) + 9.4 (DMF, density = 0.944 g/mL) + 360 (EtOAc density = 0.944 g/mL) + 400 (water) + 238 (brine density = 1.19 g/mL))] – [(0.209 (isolated product))] / 0.209 (isolated product) = 4825</p> <p>(column chromatography was not considered in <i>E</i>-factor calculation)</p>
<p><i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012, 2013–2022.</p> <p>M. Nagarjuna Reddy and K. C. Kumara Swamy</p>	<p>An oven-dried Schlenk tube with a magnetic stirrer bar was charged with CuI (10 mol % 0.05 mmol 9 mg), TMEDA (20 mol % 0.1 mmol 1 mg), and DMF (1 mL, 944 mg) under a nitrogen atmosphere. O-Alkynyl iodophenol (0.5 mmol 66 mg) and azide (0.5 mmol 74 mg) were added by syringe. The mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature, and the formation of triazole was monitored by TLC. After the complete formation of triazole, lithium tert-butoxide (3.0 equiv. 1.5 mmol, 120 mg) was added, and the mixture was heated at 140 °C for 4 h. The mixture was then cooled to ambient temperature, diluted with ethyl acetate (2 mL, 1.8 g), passed through a plug of celite, and washed with ethyl acetate (10 mL, 9.02 g). The filtrate was washed with water (10 mL 10 g) and brine (10 mL 12 g). The organic layer was evaporated and the residue purified by column chromatography on silica gel by using hexane/ethyl acetate (75:25) as eluent to afford the desired product. (Yield 70 % 0.35 mmol, 0.0977 mg)</p>	<p>Calculation of <i>E</i>-factor (0.5 mmol scale)</p> <p>(0.35 mmol, yield 70 %)=[(0.009(CuI) + 0.001(TMEDA) + 0.944 (DMF, density = 0.944 g/mL) + 0.066(O-Alkynyl iodophenol) + 0.074 (azide) + 0.120 (Lithium tert butoxide) + 10.82 (EtOAc density = 0.944 g/mL) + 10 (water) + 12 (brine density = 1.19 g/mL)) – (0.097 (isolated product))] / 0.097 (isolated product) = 349</p> <p>(column chromatography was not considered in <i>E</i>-factor calculation)</p>

Chem. Name	1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2a)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012 , 2013–2022			
METHOD:				
Substrate 1a (1.2 mmol, 488 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (292 mg, 87% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	m.p.	151-153 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 68.81; H, 4.69; N, 15.05. Found: C, 68.84; H, 4.63; N, 15.01				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.48-7.43	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.23-7.19	1	<i>m</i>	
	7.11-7.05	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.02	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	6.90	1	<i>dd</i>	1.6, 7.6
	6.82–6.78	1	<i>m</i>	
	5.53	2	<i>s</i>	
	3.92	3	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 160.9, 153.8, 139.2, 130.7, 129.6, 128.4, 127.1, 122.4, 121.8, 117.9, 114.8, 114.0, 64.5, 55.7				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 279 (18), 251 (35), 250 (38), 237 (17), 236 (100), 220 (16), 208 (31), 207 (33), 89 (15), 63 (17).				

Chem. Name	1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2a)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012 , 2013–2022			
METHOD: Substrate 1aBr (1.2 mmol, 432 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (274 mg, 82% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	m.p.	151-153 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 68.81; H, 4.69; N, 15.05. Found: C, 68.79; H, 4.64; N, 15.02				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.48-7.43	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.23-7.19	1	<i>m</i>	
	7.11-7.05	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.02	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	6.90	1	<i>dd</i>	1.6, 7.6
	6.82–6.78	1	<i>m</i>	
	5.53	2	<i>s</i>	
	3.92	3	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 160.9, 153.8, 139.2, 130.7, 129.6, 128.4, 127.1, 122.4, 121.8, 117.9, 114.8, 114.0, 64.5, 55.7				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 279 (18), 251 (35), 250 (38), 237 (17), 236 (100), 220 (16), 208 (31), 207 (33), 89 (15), 63 (17).				

Chem. Name	1-benzyl-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-<i>d</i>][1,2,3]triazole (2b)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012 , 2013–2022			
METHOD:				
Substrate 1b (1.2 mmol, 469 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (265 mg, 82% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	m.p.	141-143 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.99; H, 4.98; N, 15.96. Found: C, 73.02; H, 4.97; N, 15.99				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.39–7.30	3	<i>m</i>	
	7.24-7.18	4	<i>m</i>	
	7.01	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	6.91	1	<i>t</i>	8.0
	5.83	2	<i>s</i>	
	5.50	2	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.8, 139.9, 134.8, 130.7, 129.3, 128.5, 127.9, 126.6, 122.7, 122.2, 118.1, 114.0, 64.6, 53.2				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 263 (100), 234 (67), 116 (15), 91 (74), 89 (16), 65 (16)				

Chem. Name	1-benzyl-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2b)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012 , 2013–2022			
<p style="text-align: center;">1bBr 2b</p>				
METHOD:				
Substrate 1bBr (1.2 mmol, 413 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (253 mg, 80% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	m.p.	141-143 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.99; H, 4.98; N, 15.96. Found: C, 72.97; H, 4.96; N, 15.93				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.39–7.30	3	<i>m</i>	
	7.24-7.18	4	<i>m</i>	
	7.01	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	6.91	1	<i>t</i>	8.0
	5.83	2	<i>s</i>	
	5.50	2	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.8, 139.9, 134.8, 130.7, 129.3, 128.5, 127.9, 126.6, 122.7, 122.2, 118.1, 114.0, 64.6, 53.2				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 263 (100), 234 (67), 116 (15), 91 (74), 89 (16), 65 (16)				

Chem. Name	1-(<i>p</i>-tolyl)-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-<i>d</i>][1,2,3]triazole (2c)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012 , 2013–2022			
METHOD:				
Substrate 1c (1.2 mmol, 469 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (268 mg, 85% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	m.p.	74-77 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.99; H, 4.98; N, 15.96. Found: C, 72.96; H, 5.00; N, 15.99				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.46-7.36	4	<i>m</i>	
	7.22	1	<i>t</i>	7.2
	7.04	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	6.92	1	<i>d</i>	7.2
	6.81	1	<i>t</i>	7.6
	5.54	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.51	3	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.9, 140.6, 139.5, 134.4, 130.8, 130.4, 128.3, 125.6, 122.6, 121.9, 118.0, 114.1, 64.6, 21.5				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 263 (100), 234 (72), 233 (28), 130 (54), 118 (40), 116 (32), 89 (20), 77 (15)				

Chem. Name	1-(<i>p</i>-tolyl)-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-<i>d</i>][1,2,3]triazole (2c)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012 , 2013–2022			
<p style="text-align: center;">1cBr 2c</p>				
METHOD: Substrate 1cBr (1.2 mmol, 413 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (249 mg, 79% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	m.p.	74-77 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.99; H, 4.98; N, 15.96. Found: C, 72.95; H, 4.94; N, 15.94				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.46-7.36	4	<i>m</i>	
	7.22	1	<i>t</i>	7.2
	7.04	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	6.92	1	<i>d</i>	7.2
	6.81	1	<i>t</i>	7.6
	5.54	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.51	3	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.9, 140.6, 139.5, 134.4, 130.8, 130.4, 128.3, 125.6, 122.6, 121.9, 118.0, 114.1, 64.6, 21.5				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 263 (100), 234 (72), 233 (28), 130 (54), 118 (40), 116 (32), 89 (20), 77 (15)				

Chem. Name	1-pentyl-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2d)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Org. Lett.</i> 2010 , <i>12</i> , 2056–2059			
METHOD: Substrate 1d (1.2 mmol, 445 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale yellow crystals (265 mg, 91% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	m.p.	24-26 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 69.11 H, 7.04; N, 17.27. Found: C, 69.14; H, 7.07; N, 17.23				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.44	1	<i>d</i>	1.6
	7.42-7.29	1	<i>m</i>	
	7.10-7.02	2	<i>m</i>	
	5.46	2	<i>s</i>	
	4.60	2	<i>t</i>	7.2
	1.97	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.46-1.32	4	<i>m</i>	
	0.92	3	<i>t</i>	6.4
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.7, 132.1, 130.5, 125.1, 122.2, 122.1, 118.2, 114.2, 64.5, 50.0, 29.6, 28.6, 22.2, 13.9				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 243 (100), 214 (37), 200 (16), 187 (26), 186 (46), 173 (29), 172 (74), 160 (15), 159 (37), 158 (100), 145 (86), 130 (30), 118 (46), 89 (33), 77 (31), 63 (17)				

Chem. Name	1-pentyl-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2d)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Org. Lett.</i> 2010 , 12, 2056–2059			
<p style="text-align: center;">1dBr 2d</p>				
METHOD:				
Substrate 1dBr (1.2 mmol, 389 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale yellow crystals (254 mg, 87% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	m.p.	24-26 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 69.11 H, 7.04; N, 17.27. Found: C, 69.15; H, 7.05; N, 17.24				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.44	1	<i>d</i>	1.6
	7.42-7.29	1	<i>m</i>	
	7.10-7.02	2	<i>m</i>	
	5.46	2	<i>s</i>	
	4.60	2	<i>t</i>	7.2
	1.97	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.46-1.32	4	<i>m</i>	
0.92	3	<i>t</i>	6.4	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 153.7, 132.1, 130.5, 125.1, 122.2, 122.1, 118.2, 114.2, 64.5, 50.0, 29.6, 28.6, 22.2, 13.9				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 243 (100), 214 (37), 200 (16), 187 (26), 186 (46), 173 (29), 172 (74), 160 (15), 159 (37), 158 (100), 145 (86), 130 (30), 118 (46), 89 (33), 77 (31), 63 (17)				

Chem. Name	3-butyl-8<i>H</i>-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-<i>a</i>]isoindole (4a)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Chem. Commun.</i> 2016 , 52, 9777–9780			
METHOD:				
Substrate 3a (1.2 mmol, 409 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of ethyl acetate and 5 mL of cold hexane was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (238 mg, 93% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃	m.p.	74-75 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 73.21; H, 7.09; N, 19.70. Found: C, 73.18; H, 7.12; N, 19.73				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.62	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.54-7.41	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.38	1	<i>t</i>	7.6
	5.31	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.96	2	<i>t</i>	7.2
	1.87-1.78	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.50-1.41	2	<i>m</i>	
	0.98	3	<i>t</i>	7.2
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 140.8, 139.5, 139.5, 128.9, 128.7, 127.8, 124.3, 121.0, 51.1, 31.8, 25.8, 22.5, 14.0				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 213 (26), 184 (52), 170 (100), 168 (25), 157 (16), 156 (72), 154 (27), 142 (43), 129 (41), 115 (56), 89 (33), 63 (17)				

Chem. Name	3-butyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4a)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Chem. Commun.</i> 2016 , 52, 9777–9780			
<p>The reaction scheme shows the conversion of substrate 3aBr to product 4a. 3aBr is 3-bromo-2-(3-butyl-1H-1,2,3-triazol-5-ylmethyl)benzene. It reacts in a flow reactor (represented by a coil) to form 4a, which is 3-butyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole.</p>				
METHOD:				
Substrate 3aBr (1.2 mmol, 353 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of ethyl acetate and 5 mL of cold hexane was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (223 mg, 87% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃	m.p.	74-75 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 73.21; H, 7.09; N, 19.70. Found: C, 73.19; H, 7.06; N, 19.66				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.62	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.54-7.41	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.38	1	<i>t</i>	7.6
	5.31	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.96	2	<i>t</i>	7.2
	1.87-1.78	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.50-1.41	2	<i>m</i>	
	0.98	3	<i>t</i>	7.2
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 140.8, 139.5, 139.5, 128.9, 128.7, 127.8, 124.3, 121.0, 51.1, 31.8, 25.8, 22.5, 14.0				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 213 (26), 184 (52), 170 (100), 168 (25), 157 (16), 156 (72), 154 (27), 142 (43), 129 (41), 115 (56), 89 (33), 63 (17)				

Chem. Name	3-phenyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4b)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Adv. Synth. Catal.</i> 2008 , 350, 741–748			
METHOD:				
Substrate 3b (1.2 mmol, 433 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (252 mg, 90% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃	m.p.	155-158 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 77.23; H, 4.75; N, 18.01. Found: C, 77.27; H, 4.72; N, 18.05				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.94	2	<i>d</i>	7.2
	7.88	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.54-7.50	3	<i>m</i>	
	7.48-7.37	3	<i>m</i>	
	5.35	2	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 141.2, 139.3, 139.0, 131.3, 129.0, 128.8, 128.4, 128.2, 128.1, 127.0, 124.2, 121.3, 51.0				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 233 (8), 205 (71), 204 (100), 176 (25), 102 (52), 89 (54), 63 (18)				

Chem. Name	3-hexyl-8<i>H</i>-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-<i>a</i>]isoindole (4c)			
Lit. Ref.				
METHOD:				
Substrate 3c (1.2 mmol, 443 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of ethyl acetate and 5 mL of cold hexane was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (260 mg, 90% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₃	m.p.	88-91 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 74.65; H, 7.94; N, 17.41. Found: C, 74.69; H, 7.97; N, 17.39				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.59	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.51-7.40	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.36	1	<i>t</i>	7.2
	5.28	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.93	2	<i>t</i>	7.6
	1.84-1.76	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.48-1.25	6	<i>m</i>	
	0.87	3	<i>t</i>	6.8
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 140.8, 139.4, 128.8, 128.6, 128.4, 127.8, 124.2, 120.9, 51.0, 31.7, 29.6, 29.1, 26.0, 22.7, 14.2				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 241 (10), 212 (23), 184 (24), 171 (21), 170 (100), 157 (15), 156 (55), 143 (25), 129 (23), 115 (36), 89 (18)				

Chem. Name	3-(cyclopentylmethyl)-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4d)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Tetrahedron</i> 2010 , 66, 8846–8853			
METHOD:				
Substrate 3d (1.2 mmol, 440 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (264 mg, 92% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃	m.p.	107-110 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 75.28; H, 7.16; N, 17.56. Found: C, 75.22; H, 7.17; N, 17.59				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.62	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.52-7.43	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.37	1	<i>td</i>	7.6, 1.2
	5.29	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.95	2	<i>d</i>	7.2
	2.41-2.30	1	<i>m</i>	
	1.85-1.74	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.70-1.62	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.58-1.53	2	<i>m</i>	
1.34-1.25	2	<i>m</i>		
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 140.8, 139.6, 138.9, 128.8, 128.7, 127.8, 124.3, 120.9, 51.0, 40.7, 32.5, 31.8, 25.1				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 239 (15), 210 (63), 183 (33), 182 (100), 168 (28), 167 (17), 143 (36), 115 (18), 89 (21)				

Chem. Name	3-cyclohexyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4e)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Tetrahedron</i> 2010 , 66, 8846–8853			
METHOD:				
Substrate 3e (1.2 mmol, 440 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (238 mg, 83% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃	m.p.	128-130 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 75.28; H, 7.16; N, 17.56. Found: C, 75.26; H, 7.20; N, 17.55				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.68	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.51-7.43	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.37	1	<i>t</i>	7.6
	5.29	2	<i>s</i>	
	3.08-2.96	1	<i>m</i>	
	2.11-2.00	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.94-1.85	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.82-1.65	3	<i>m</i>	
1.54-1.31	3	<i>m</i>		
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 144.8, 140.8, 138.7, 128.8, 128.7, 127.8, 124.2, 121.6, 60.0, 36.4, 32.8, 26.6, 26.2				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 239 (7), 211 (19), 210 (61), 183 (43), 182 (100), 168 (37), 167 (26), 154 (26), 130 (16), 127 (16), 115 (16), 89 (16)				

Chem. Name	3-(<i>p</i>-tolyl)-8<i>H</i>-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-<i>a</i>]isoindole (4f)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Tetrahedron</i> 2010 , 66, 8846–8853			
METHOD:				
Substrate 3f (1.2 mmol, 450 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (273 mg, 92% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃	m.p.	163-164 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 77.71; H, 5.30; N, 16.99. Found: C, 77.67; H, 5.32; N, 16.96				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.89	1	<i>d</i>	7.2
	7.86-7.82	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.53	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.49-7.40	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.35-7.31	2	<i>m</i>	
	5.36	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.44	3	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 141.2, 139.5, 138.9, 138.2, 129.7, 128.9, 128.5, 128.4, 128.4, 127.0, 124.3, 121.3, 51.0, 21.5				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 247 (8), 219 (61), 218 (100), 204 (72), 189 (21), 166 (15), 109 (37), 89 (21), 63 (24)				

Chem. Name	3-((2-iodophenoxy)methyl)-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4g)			
Lit. Ref.				
METHOD:				
Substrate 3g (1.2 mmol, 620 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (383 mg, 82% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ IN ₃ O		m.p.	294-296 °C (decomp.)
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 49.38; H, 3.11; N, 10.80. Found: C, 49.34; H, 3.08; N, 10.83				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.98	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	7.75	1	<i>dd</i>	1.2, 8.0
	7.48	2	<i>t</i>	6.8
	7.42-7.38	1	<i>m</i>	
	7.28-7.24	1	<i>m</i>	
	7.07	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	6.70	1	<i>td</i>	8.0, 1.2
	5.53	2	<i>s</i>	
5.32	2	<i>s</i>		
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 156.8, 142.0, 140.9, 139.8, 134.7, 129.7, 129.0, 128.7, 127.6, 124.0, 123.6, 123.2, 113.1, 86.5, 63.8, 51.5				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 389 (2), 319 (23), 290 (100), 235 (21), 234 (64), 221 (17), 220 (54), 204 (32), 179 (40), 130 (35), 65 (16)				

Chem. Name	Ethyl 4-(4-butyl-1-phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazol-5-yl)benzoate (7a)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Chem. Commun.</i> 2016 , <i>52</i> , 9777–9780			
<p style="text-align: center;"> 5a 6b 7a </p>				
METHOD: Triazole 5a (1.2 mmol, 241 mg), 6b (3.6 mmol, 825 mg, 588 μ l) TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrhor apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1) to give the pure product as a colorless oil (327 mg, 78% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	m.p.		
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.18; H, 6.63; N, 12.03. Found: C, 72.15; H, 6.69; N, 11.99				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.98-7.92	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.33-7.29	3	<i>m</i>	
	7.21-7.10	4	<i>m</i>	
	4.30	2	<i>q</i>	6.8
	2.67	2	<i>t</i>	7.6
	1.67-1.58	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.34-1.22	5	<i>m</i>	
	0.80	3	<i>t</i>	7.2
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 165.89, 146.7, 136.6, 132.9, 132.2, 130.8, 129.9, 129.5, 129.3, 129.0, 124.9, 61.3, 31.7, 24.9, 22.5, 14.3, 13.8				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 349 (7), 321 (25), 279 (21), 278 (100), 175 (35), 147 (18), 104 (16), 77 (39)				

Chem. Name	Ethyl 4-(4-butyl-1-phenyl-1<i>H</i>-1,2,3-triazol-5-yl)benzoate (7a)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Chem. Commun.</i> 2016 , <i>52</i> , 9777–9780			
<p style="text-align: center;"> <chem>C1=CN=C(N1c2ccccc2)C=Cn3ccccc3</chem> + <chem>CCOC(=O)c1ccc(I)cc1</chem> $\xrightarrow{\text{flow reactor}}$ <chem>CCOC(=O)c1ccc(cc1)C2=C(N2c3ccccc3)C=Cn4ccccc4</chem> </p> <p style="text-align: center;"> 5a 6a 7a </p>				
METHOD:				
<p>Triazole 5a (1.2 mmol, 241 mg), 6a (3.6 mmol, 994 mg, 605 μl) TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO₂H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1) to give the pure product as a colorless oil (343 mg, 82% yield).</p>				
Mol Formula	$C_{21}H_{23}N_3O_2$	m.p.		
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.18; H, 6.63; N, 12.03. Found: C, 72.14; H, 6.67; N, 12.06				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.98-7.92	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.33-7.29	3	<i>m</i>	
	7.21-7.10	4	<i>m</i>	
	4.30	2	<i>q</i>	6.8
	2.67	2	<i>t</i>	7.6
	1.67-1.58	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.34-1.22	5	<i>m</i>	
	0.80	3	<i>t</i>	7.2
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 165.89, 146.7, 136.6, 132.9, 132.2, 130.8, 129.9, 129.5, 129.3, 129.0, 124.9, 61.3, 31.7, 24.9, 22.5, 14.3, 13.8				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 349 (7), 321 (25), 279 (21), 278 (100), 175 (35), 147 (18), 104 (16), 77 (39)				

Chem. Name	Ethyl 4-(4-butyl-1-(<i>p</i>-tolyl)-1<i>H</i>-1,2,3-triazol-5-yl)benzoate (7b)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Chem. Commun.</i> 2016 , <i>52</i> , 9777–9780			
METHOD:				
<p>Triazole 5b (1.2 mmol, 258 mg), 6b (3.6 mmol, 825 mg, 588 μl) TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO₂H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1) to give the pure product as a colorless oil (371 mg, 85% yield).</p>				
Mol Formula	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	m.p.		
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.70; H, 6.93; N, 11.56. Found: C, 72.66; H, 6.94; N, 11.52				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	8.05-7.98	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.25-7.20	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.13	4	<i>s</i>	
	4.36	2	<i>q</i>	7.2
	2.73	2	<i>t</i>	7.6
	2.33	3	<i>s</i>	
	1.75-1.65	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.39-1.30	5	<i>m</i>	
0.86	3	<i>t</i>	7.2	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 165.89, 146.48, 139.1, 134.1, 132.9, 132.3, 130.7, 129.9, 129.8, 129.5, 124.7, 61.3, 31.7, 24.9, 22.4, 21.1, 14.3, 13.8				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 363 (2), 334 (15), 335 (48), 293 (21), 292 (100), 175 (25), 147 (16), 104 (15), 77 (41), 51 (15)				

Chem. Name	Ethyl 4-(4-butyl-1-(<i>p</i>-tolyl)-1<i>H</i>-1,2,3-triazol-5-yl)benzoate (7b)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Chem. Commun.</i> 2016 , <i>52</i> , 9777–9780			
<p style="text-align: center;"> 5b 6a 7b </p>				
METHOD: Triazole 5b (1.2 mmol, 258 mg), 6a (3.6 mmol, 994 mg, 605 μ l) TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1) to give the pure product as a colorless oil (379 mg, 87% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	m.p.		
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.70; H, 6.93; N, 11.56. Found: C, 72.67; H, 6.89; N, 11.53				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	8.05-7.98	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.25-7.20	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.13	4	<i>s</i>	
	4.36	2	<i>q</i>	7.2
	2.73	2	<i>t</i>	7.6
	2.33	3	<i>s</i>	
	1.75-1.65	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.39-1.30	5	<i>m</i>	
	0.86	3	<i>t</i>	7.2
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 165.89, 146.48, 139.1, 134.1, 132.9, 132.3, 130.7, 129.9, 129.8, 129.5, 124.7, 61.3, 31.7, 24.9, 22.4, 21.1, 14.3, 13.8				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 363 (2), 334 (15), 335 (48), 293 (21), 292 (100), 175 (25), 147 (16), 104 (15), 77 (41), 51 (15)				

Green Chemistry
1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2a)

Green Chemistry
1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2a)

Green Chemistry
1-benzyl-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2b)

Green Chemistry
1-benzyl-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2b)

Green Chemistry
1-(p-tolyl)-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2c)

Green Chemistry
1-(p-tolyl)-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2c)

1-pentyl-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2d)

1-pentyl-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2d)

Green Chemistry
3-butyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4a)

3-phenyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4b)

Green Chemistry
3-phenyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4b)

Green Chemistry
3-hexyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4c)

3-hexyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4c)

Green Chemistry
3-(cyclopentylmethyl)-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4d)

Green Chemistry
3-(cyclopentylmethyl)-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4d)

3-cyclohexyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4e)

3-cyclohexyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4e)

Green Chemistry
3-(p-tolyl)-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4f)

3-(p-tolyl)-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4f)

3-((2-iodophenoxy)methyl)-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4g)

Green Chemistry
ethyl 4-(4-butyl-1-phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazol-5-yl)benzoate (7a)

ethyl 4-(4-butyl-1-phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazol-5-yl)benzoate (7a)

Green Chemistry
ethyl 4-(4-butyl-1-(p-tolyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazol-5-yl)benzoate (7b)

Green Chemistry
ethyl 4-(4-butyl-1-(p-tolyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazol-5-yl)benzoate (7b)

ELECTRONIC SUPPORTING INFORMATION**A continuous flow approach for the C–H functionalization of 1,2,3-triazoles in γ -valerolactone as biomass-derived medium**

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Page	ESI 25–50	Copies of the ¹ H and ¹³ C NMR spectra

General Information

Unless otherwise stated, all solvents and reagents were used as obtained from commercial sources without further purification. GC analyses were performed using a Hewlett-Packard HP 5890A equipped with a capillary column DB-35MS (30 m, 0.53 mm) and a FID detector. GC-EIMS analyses were carried out using a Hewlett-Packard HP 6890N Network GC system/5975 MassSelective Detector equipped with an electron impact ionizer at 70 eV. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-ADVANCE 400 MHz (^1H at 400 MHz and ^{13}C at 100.6 MHz). The deuterated solvent used was CDCl_3 . Elemental Analyses were conducted on a Fisons EA1108CHN. Melting points were measured on a Büchi 510.

General larger scale procedures and E-factor calculations

General flow procedure using packed Pd/C reactor and organic TBAAc as base

(amounts and calculation for representative 100 mmol scale)

Main features:

- solvent recovery (90 %)
- catalyst safely packed into the reactor
- product isolation by re-crystallization

A premixed mixture of **1a** (100 mmol, 0.041 Kg), TBAAc (200 mmol, 0.060 Kg) and MesCO_2H (30 mol %, 30 mmol, 0.0050 Kg) in GVL (660 mL, 0.15M, 0.66 Kg) was charged into a glass column functioning as a reservoir. The equipment was connected, by using the appropriate valves, to a pump and installed into a box thermostated at 120 °C. The reaction mixture was continuously pumped (flow rate: 0.25 mL·min⁻¹; residence time: 80 min) through the catalyst column and the reaction was monitored by GC. Product was collected in fractions and palladium content of the GVL solution was periodically measured by MP-AES analysis. GVL was distilled from the reaction mixture and 0.594 Kg of GVL (90 % of the initial amount) was recovered as pure compound (confirmed by $^1\text{H-NMR}$). Resulting oil was dissolved in acetone (40 mL, 0.031 Kg), and water (400 mL, 0.4 Kg) was added to precipitate pale brown crystals. Filtration and in vacuo drying gave pure compound (87 mmol, 0.024 Kg, 87 %).

E-factor (100 mmol scale) = $[(0.041_{(\text{substrates})} + 0.060_{(\text{TBAAc})} + 0.0050_{(\text{MesCO}_2\text{H})} + 0.66_{(\text{GVL})} + 0.4_{(\text{water})} + 0.031_{(\text{acetone})}) - (0.594_{(\text{recovered GVL})} + 0.0242_{(\text{isolated product})})] / 0.0242_{(\text{isolated product})} = \underline{\underline{23.9}}$.

Optimized larger scale batch procedure based on our literature protocol using Pd/C as catalyst and KTFA as base (100 mmol scale)

Main features:

- solvent recovery (90 %)
- product isolation by re-crystallization
- optimized amount of water used for washing the catalyst from inorganic salts

Pd/C (0.0054 Kg, 5.0 mol %, 5 mmol), MesCO₂H (0.005 Kg, 30 mol %, 30 mmol), KTFA (0.044 Kg, 300 mmol), substrate (0.0294 Kg, 100 mmol) in GVL (400 mL, 0.42 Kg) was charged into a round bottom flask equipped with magnetic stirring bar and reacted under N₂ for 16 h at 150 °C. After cooling to ambient temperature, the reaction mixture was filtered to separate the catalyst. The catalyst was washed with GVL (200 mL, 0.2 Kg) in order to extract residual product from the catalyst, followed by water (0.4 L, 0.4 Kg), and EtOH (0.2 L, 0.1596 Kg) to wash the catalyst from salts. To the remaining residue, EtOH (0.4 L, 0.318 Kg) was added and the mixture was treated with ultrasound in a sonication bath for 3 h. The solvent was removed after filtration and the residual Pd/C was dried in vacuum at 60 °C overnight. The recovered material was used for the subsequent run (99 % of the total mass of the catalyst was recovered, 0.0053 Kg). The GVL solution containing the products of reaction was distilled (90 % of the total mass of solvent was recovered as pure, 0.558 Kg). Resulting oil was dissolved in ethyl acetate (20 mL, 0.018 Kg), and hexane (0.4 L, 0.26 Kg) was added to precipitate pale brown crystals. Filtration and drying of the solid under vacuum afforded the pure product 3-*n*-Butyl-8*H*-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-*a*]isoindole (0.016 kg, 75 %).

$$\text{E-factor (100 mmol scale)} = [(0.0294_{(\text{triazole})} + 0.0054_{(\text{Pd/C})} + 0.0050_{(\text{MesCO}_2\text{H})} + 0.0442_{(\text{KTFA})} + 0.62_{(\text{GVL})} + 0.4_{(\text{water})} + 0.4776_{(\text{EtOH})} + 0.018_{(\text{EtOAc})} + 0.26_{(\text{hexane})}) - (0.0053_{(\text{recovered Pd/C})} + 0.558_{(\text{recovered GVL})} + 0.016_{(\text{isolated product})})] / 0.016_{(\text{isolated product})} = \mathbf{80}$$

Experiment replicating flow conditions in batch

In order to analyze the differences between flow and batch conditions, we performed a batch reaction using the same catalyst/reactants ratio present at any time in the flow reactor. Therefore, substrate **1a** (1.2 mmol, 0.48 g), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 0.72 g), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL, 7.73 g) and MesCO₂H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 0.06 g), were consecutively added in vial followed by Pd/C (1.88 mmol, 2g). The reaction mixture was stirred at 120 °C and periodically analyzed by GC analysis. After 80 min conversion to product was complete. The reaction mixture was cooled to ambient temperature, and filtered to separate the catalyst. The catalyst was washed first with GVL (12 mL, 12.06 g), in order to extract residual product and TBAAc, followed by EtOH (15 mL, 11.83 g), to wash the catalyst from GVL. Residual Pd/C was dried in vacuum at 60 °C overnight. The recovered material was used for the subsequent reaction run (97 % of the total mass of the catalyst was recovered, 1.94 g). The GVL solution containing the products of reaction was distilled (90 % of the total mass of solvent was recovered as pure, 54.27 g). Resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone (0.4 g) and 5 mL of cold water (5 g) was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (0.285 g, 85 % yield).

$$\text{E-factor:} = [(0.48_{(\text{substrates})} + 0.72_{(\text{TBAAc})} + 0.06_{(\text{MesCO}_2\text{H})} + 7.73_{(\text{GVL})} + 12.06_{(\text{GVL wash})} + 11.83_{(\text{EtOH wash})} + 0.4_{(\text{acetone})} + 5_{(\text{water})}) - (17.81_{(\text{recovered GVL})} + 1.94_{(\text{recovered catalyst})} + 0.285_{(\text{isolated product})})] / 0.285_{(\text{isolated product})} = \mathbf{64}$$

Concentration of Pd measured by MP-AES analysis in the GVL solution: **2.74 ppm**

Calculation of E-factors for Representative Literature Procedures

The procedures and *E*-factor calculations described below are representative. In the evaluation of the results obtained, it should be considered that these procedures have not been specifically optimized for larger scale and/or waste minimization protocols.

Reference	General Procedure	E-factor calculation
<p><i>Org. Lett.</i>, 2010, 12, 2056–2059</p> <p>Lutz Ackermann, Rajkumar Jeyachandran, Harish K. Potukuchi, Petr Novák and Lea Büttner</p>	<p>Pd(OAc)₂ (11.2 mg, 0.05 mmol, 5.0 mol %), Cu(OAc)₂·H₂O (200 mg, 1.00 mmol), PivOH (500 mg, 4.90 mmol) and triazole 1a (287 mg, 1.00 mmol) in dry toluene (3 mL) were stirred in a sealed tube at 140 °C for 20 h. H₂O (50 mL) was added at ambient temperature, and the resulting mixture was extracted with EtOAc (3 x 50 mL). The combined organic layers were washed with sat. aq. NH₄Cl (50 mL), H₂O (50 mL) and brine (50 mL), dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated in vacuo. The remaining residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (n-hexane/EtOAc = 10/1 → 5/1) to yield 2a (274 mg, 96%) as a yellow oil.</p>	<p>Calculation of <i>E</i>-factor (1 mmol scale)</p> <p>(0.96 mmol, yield 96%)=[(0.287(triazole) + 0.011(Pd(OAc)₂) + 0.200(Cu(OAc)₂) + 0.500(PivOH) + 2.61 (toluene, density = 0.87 g/mL) + 53 (NH₄Cl density = 1.06 g/mL) + 135 (EtOAc density = 0.902 g/mL) + 150 (water))] – [(0.274 (isolated product))] / 0.274 (isolated product) = 1245</p> <p>(column chromatography was not considered in <i>E</i>-factor calculation)</p>
<p><i>RSC Adv.</i>, 2013, 3, 2710–2719</p> <p>Chung-Yu Chen, Cheng-Hao Yang, Wan-Ping Hu, Jaya Kishore Vandavasi, Mei-Ing Chunga and Jeh-Jeng Wang</p>	<p>The starting material (4-((2-iodophenoxy)methyl)-1-phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazole derivatives) (1.0 mmol, 377 mg) was dissolved in the dry N,N-dimethylformamide (10 mL, 9.4 g), followed by treating with tetrabutylammonium iodide (TBAI, 3.0 mmol 967 mg), after which Pd(OAc)₂ 5 mol% (5 mg) was added to the reaction and stirred for 6–12 h at 100 °C. Progress was monitored by TLC to confirm the starting materials had been consumed and then the reaction mixture was poured out on ice cooled water and extracted with ethyl acetate (2 x 200 mL 360 g) and the combined organic layers were washed with water (2 x 200 mL 400 g), brine (1 x 200 mL 238 g), dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. Crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel 0.040–0.633 mm, Ethyl acetate: Hexane = 1:3) to obtain a white solid 209.3 mg (84%)</p>	<p>Calculation of <i>E</i>-factor (1 mmol scale)</p> <p>(0.84 mmol, yield 84%)=[(0.377(triazole) + 0.005(Pd(OAc)₂) + 0.967(TBAI) + 9.4 (DMF, density = 0.944 g/mL) + 360 (EtOAc density = 0.944 g/mL) + 400 (water) + 238 (brine density = 1.19 g/mL))] – [(0.209 (isolated product))] / 0.209 (isolated product) = 4825</p> <p>(column chromatography was not considered in <i>E</i>-factor calculation)</p>
<p><i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012, 2013–2022.</p> <p>M. Nagarjuna Reddy and K. C. Kumara Swamy</p>	<p>An oven-dried Schlenk tube with a magnetic stirrer bar was charged with CuI (10 mol % 0.05 mmol 9 mg), TMEDA (20 mol % 0.1 mmol 1 mg), and DMF (1 mL, 944 mg) under a nitrogen atmosphere. O-Alkynyl iodophenol (0.5 mmol 66 mg) and azide (0.5 mmol 74 mg) were added by syringe. The mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature, and the formation of triazole was monitored by TLC. After the complete formation of triazole, lithium tert-butoxide (3.0 equiv. 1.5 mmol, 120 mg) was added, and the mixture was heated at 140 °C for 4 h. The mixture was then cooled to ambient temperature, diluted with ethyl acetate (2 mL, 1.8 g), passed through a plug of celite, and washed with ethyl acetate (10 mL, 9.02 g). The filtrate was washed with water (10 mL 10 g) and brine (10 mL 12 g). The organic layer was evaporated and the residue purified by column chromatography on silica gel by using hexane/ethyl acetate (75:25) as eluent to afford the desired product. (Yield 70 % 0.35 mmol, 0.0977 mg)</p>	<p>Calculation of <i>E</i>-factor (0.5 mmol scale)</p> <p>(0.35 mmol, yield 70 %)=[(0.009(CuI) + 0.001(TMEDA) + 0.944 (DMF, density = 0.944 g/mL) + 0.066(O-Alkynyl iodophenol) + 0.074 (azide) + 0.120 (Lithium tert butoxide) + 10.82 (EtOAc density = 0.944 g/mL) + 10 (water) + 12 (brine density = 1.19 g/mL)) – (0.097 (isolated product))] / 0.097 (isolated product) = 349</p> <p>(column chromatography was not considered in <i>E</i>-factor calculation)</p>

Chem. Name	1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2a)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012 , 2013–2022			
METHOD:				
Substrate 1a (1.2 mmol, 488 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (292 mg, 87% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	m.p.	151-153 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 68.81; H, 4.69; N, 15.05. Found: C, 68.84; H, 4.63; N, 15.01				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.48-7.43	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.23-7.19	1	<i>m</i>	
	7.11-7.05	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.02	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	6.90	1	<i>dd</i>	1.6, 7.6
	6.82–6.78	1	<i>m</i>	
	5.53	2	<i>s</i>	
	3.92	3	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 160.9, 153.8, 139.2, 130.7, 129.6, 128.4, 127.1, 122.4, 121.8, 117.9, 114.8, 114.0, 64.5, 55.7				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 279 (18), 251 (35), 250 (38), 237 (17), 236 (100), 220 (16), 208 (31), 207 (33), 89 (15), 63 (17).				

Chem. Name	1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2a)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012 , 2013–2022			
METHOD:				
Substrate 1aBr (1.2 mmol, 432 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (274 mg, 82% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	m.p.	151-153 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 68.81; H, 4.69; N, 15.05. Found: C, 68.79; H, 4.64; N, 15.02				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.48-7.43	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.23-7.19	1	<i>m</i>	
	7.11-7.05	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.02	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	6.90	1	<i>dd</i>	1.6, 7.6
	6.82–6.78	1	<i>m</i>	
	5.53	2	<i>s</i>	
	3.92	3	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 160.9, 153.8, 139.2, 130.7, 129.6, 128.4, 127.1, 122.4, 121.8, 117.9, 114.8, 114.0, 64.5, 55.7				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 279 (18), 251 (35), 250 (38), 237 (17), 236 (100), 220 (16), 208 (31), 207 (33), 89 (15), 63 (17).				

Chem. Name	1-benzyl-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-<i>d</i>][1,2,3]triazole (2b)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012 , 2013–2022			
METHOD:				
Substrate 1b (1.2 mmol, 469 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (265 mg, 82% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	m.p.	141-143 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.99; H, 4.98; N, 15.96. Found: C, 73.02; H, 4.97; N, 15.99				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.39–7.30	3	<i>m</i>	
	7.24-7.18	4	<i>m</i>	
	7.01	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	6.91	1	<i>t</i>	8.0
	5.83	2	<i>s</i>	
	5.50	2	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.8, 139.9, 134.8, 130.7, 129.3, 128.5, 127.9, 126.6, 122.7, 122.2, 118.1, 114.0, 64.6, 53.2				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 263 (100), 234 (67), 116 (15), 91 (74), 89 (16), 65 (16)				

Chem. Name	1-benzyl-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2b)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012 , 2013–2022			
METHOD:				
Substrate 1bBr (1.2 mmol, 413 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (253 mg, 80% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	m.p.	141-143 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.99; H, 4.98; N, 15.96. Found: C, 72.97; H, 4.96; N, 15.93				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.39–7.30	3	<i>m</i>	
	7.24-7.18	4	<i>m</i>	
	7.01	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	6.91	1	<i>t</i>	8.0
	5.83	2	<i>s</i>	
	5.50	2	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.8, 139.9, 134.8, 130.7, 129.3, 128.5, 127.9, 126.6, 122.7, 122.2, 118.1, 114.0, 64.6, 53.2				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 263 (100), 234 (67), 116 (15), 91 (74), 89 (16), 65 (16)				

Chem. Name	1-(<i>p</i>-tolyl)-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-<i>d</i>][1,2,3]triazole (2c)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012 , 2013–2022			
METHOD:				
Substrate 1c (1.2 mmol, 469 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (268 mg, 85% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	m.p.	74-77 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.99; H, 4.98; N, 15.96. Found: C, 72.96; H, 5.00; N, 15.99				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.46-7.36	4	<i>m</i>	
	7.22	1	<i>t</i>	7.2
	7.04	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	6.92	1	<i>d</i>	7.2
	6.81	1	<i>t</i>	7.6
	5.54	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.51	3	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.9, 140.6, 139.5, 134.4, 130.8, 130.4, 128.3, 125.6, 122.6, 121.9, 118.0, 114.1, 64.6, 21.5				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 263 (100), 234 (72), 233 (28), 130 (54), 118 (40), 116 (32), 89 (20), 77 (15)				

Chem. Name	1-(<i>p</i>-tolyl)-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-<i>d</i>][1,2,3]triazole (2c)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Eur. J. Org. Chem.</i> 2012 , 2013–2022			
<p style="text-align: center;">1cBr 2c</p>				
METHOD:				
Substrate 1cBr (1.2 mmol, 413 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (249 mg, 79% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	m.p.	74-77 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.99; H, 4.98; N, 15.96. Found: C, 72.95; H, 4.94; N, 15.94				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.46-7.36	4	<i>m</i>	
	7.22	1	<i>t</i>	7.2
	7.04	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	6.92	1	<i>d</i>	7.2
	6.81	1	<i>t</i>	7.6
	5.54	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.51	3	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.9, 140.6, 139.5, 134.4, 130.8, 130.4, 128.3, 125.6, 122.6, 121.9, 118.0, 114.1, 64.6, 21.5				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 263 (100), 234 (72), 233 (28), 130 (54), 118 (40), 116 (32), 89 (20), 77 (15)				

Chem. Name	1-pentyl-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2d)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Org. Lett.</i> 2010 , <i>12</i> , 2056–2059			
METHOD: Substrate 1d (1.2 mmol, 445 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale yellow crystals (265 mg, 91% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	m.p.	24-26 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 69.11 H, 7.04; N, 17.27. Found: C, 69.14; H, 7.07; N, 17.23				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.44	1	<i>d</i>	1.6
	7.42-7.29	1	<i>m</i>	
	7.10-7.02	2	<i>m</i>	
	5.46	2	<i>s</i>	
	4.60	2	<i>t</i>	7.2
	1.97	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.46-1.32	4	<i>m</i>	
	0.92	3	<i>t</i>	6.4
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.7, 132.1, 130.5, 125.1, 122.2, 122.1, 118.2, 114.2, 64.5, 50.0, 29.6, 28.6, 22.2, 13.9				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 243 (100), 214 (37), 200 (16), 187 (26), 186 (46), 173 (29), 172 (74), 160 (15), 159 (37), 158 (100), 145 (86), 130 (30), 118 (46), 89 (33), 77 (31), 63 (17)				

Chem. Name	1-pentyl-1,4-dihydrochromeno[3,4-d][1,2,3]triazole (2d)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Org. Lett.</i> 2010 , 12, 2056–2059			
<p style="text-align: center;">1dBr 2d</p>				
METHOD:				
Substrate 1dBr (1.2 mmol, 389 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale yellow crystals (254 mg, 87% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	m.p.	24-26 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 69.11 H, 7.04; N, 17.27. Found: C, 69.15; H, 7.05; N, 17.24				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.44	1	<i>d</i>	1.6
	7.42-7.29	1	<i>m</i>	
	7.10-7.02	2	<i>m</i>	
	5.46	2	<i>s</i>	
	4.60	2	<i>t</i>	7.2
	1.97	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.46-1.32	4	<i>m</i>	
0.92	3	<i>t</i>	6.4	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 153.7, 132.1, 130.5, 125.1, 122.2, 122.1, 118.2, 114.2, 64.5, 50.0, 29.6, 28.6, 22.2, 13.9				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 243 (100), 214 (37), 200 (16), 187 (26), 186 (46), 173 (29), 172 (74), 160 (15), 159 (37), 158 (100), 145 (86), 130 (30), 118 (46), 89 (33), 77 (31), 63 (17)				

Chem. Name	3-butyl-8<i>H</i>-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-<i>a</i>]isoindole (4a)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Chem. Commun.</i> 2016 , 52, 9777–9780			
METHOD:				
Substrate 3a (1.2 mmol, 409 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of ethyl acetate and 5 mL of cold hexane was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (238 mg, 93% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃	m.p.	74-75 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 73.21; H, 7.09; N, 19.70. Found: C, 73.18; H, 7.12; N, 19.73				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.62	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.54-7.41	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.38	1	<i>t</i>	7.6
	5.31	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.96	2	<i>t</i>	7.2
	1.87-1.78	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.50-1.41	2	<i>m</i>	
	0.98	3	<i>t</i>	7.2
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 140.8, 139.5, 139.5, 128.9, 128.7, 127.8, 124.3, 121.0, 51.1, 31.8, 25.8, 22.5, 14.0				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 213 (26), 184 (52), 170 (100), 168 (25), 157 (16), 156 (72), 154 (27), 142 (43), 129 (41), 115 (56), 89 (33), 63 (17)				

Chem. Name	3-butyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4a)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Chem. Commun.</i> 2016 , 52, 9777–9780			
METHOD:				
Substrate 3aBr (1.2 mmol, 353 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of ethyl acetate and 5 mL of cold hexane was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (223 mg, 87% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃	m.p.	74-75 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 73.21; H, 7.09; N, 19.70. Found: C, 73.19; H, 7.06; N, 19.66				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.62	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.54-7.41	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.38	1	<i>t</i>	7.6
	5.31	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.96	2	<i>t</i>	7.2
	1.87-1.78	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.50-1.41	2	<i>m</i>	
	0.98	3	<i>t</i>	7.2
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 140.8, 139.5, 139.5, 128.9, 128.7, 127.8, 124.3, 121.0, 51.1, 31.8, 25.8, 22.5, 14.0				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 213 (26), 184 (52), 170 (100), 168 (25), 157 (16), 156 (72), 154 (27), 142 (43), 129 (41), 115 (56), 89 (33), 63 (17)				

Chem. Name	3-phenyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4b)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Adv. Synth. Catal.</i> 2008 , 350, 741–748			
METHOD:				
Substrate 3b (1.2 mmol, 433 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (252 mg, 90% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃	m.p.	155-158 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 77.23; H, 4.75; N, 18.01. Found: C, 77.27; H, 4.72; N, 18.05				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.94	2	<i>d</i>	7.2
	7.88	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.54-7.50	3	<i>m</i>	
	7.48-7.37	3	<i>m</i>	
	5.35	2	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 141.2, 139.3, 139.0, 131.3, 129.0, 128.8, 128.4, 128.2, 128.1, 127.0, 124.2, 121.3, 51.0				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 233 (8), 205 (71), 204 (100), 176 (25), 102 (52), 89 (54), 63 (18)				

Chem. Name	3-hexyl-8<i>H</i>-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-<i>a</i>]isoindole (4c)			
Lit. Ref.				
METHOD:				
Substrate 3c (1.2 mmol, 443 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of ethyl acetate and 5 mL of cold hexane was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (260 mg, 90% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₃	m.p.	88-91 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 74.65; H, 7.94; N, 17.41. Found: C, 74.69; H, 7.97; N, 17.39				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.59	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.51-7.40	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.36	1	<i>t</i>	7.2
	5.28	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.93	2	<i>t</i>	7.6
	1.84-1.76	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.48-1.25	6	<i>m</i>	
	0.87	3	<i>t</i>	6.8
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 140.8, 139.4, 128.8, 128.6, 128.4, 127.8, 124.2, 120.9, 51.0, 31.7, 29.6, 29.1, 26.0, 22.7, 14.2				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 241 (10), 212 (23), 184 (24), 171 (21), 170 (100), 157 (15), 156 (55), 143 (25), 129 (23), 115 (36), 89 (18)				

Chem. Name	3-(cyclopentylmethyl)-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4d)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Tetrahedron</i> 2010 , 66, 8846–8853			
METHOD:				
Substrate 3d (1.2 mmol, 440 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (264 mg, 92% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃	m.p.	107-110 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 75.28; H, 7.16; N, 17.56. Found: C, 75.22; H, 7.17; N, 17.59				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.62	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.52-7.43	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.37	1	<i>td</i>	7.6, 1.2
	5.29	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.95	2	<i>d</i>	7.2
	2.41-2.30	1	<i>m</i>	
	1.85-1.74	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.70-1.62	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.58-1.53	2	<i>m</i>	
1.34-1.25	2	<i>m</i>		
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 140.8, 139.6, 138.9, 128.8, 128.7, 127.8, 124.3, 120.9, 51.0, 40.7, 32.5, 31.8, 25.1				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 239 (15), 210 (63), 183 (33), 182 (100), 168 (28), 167 (17), 143 (36), 115 (18), 89 (21)				

Chem. Name	3-cyclohexyl-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4e)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Tetrahedron</i> 2010 , 66, 8846–8853			
METHOD:				
Substrate 3e (1.2 mmol, 440 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (238 mg, 83% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃	m.p.	128-130 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 75.28; H, 7.16; N, 17.56. Found: C, 75.26; H, 7.20; N, 17.55				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.68	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.51-7.43	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.37	1	<i>t</i>	7.6
	5.29	2	<i>s</i>	
	3.08-2.96	1	<i>m</i>	
	2.11-2.00	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.94-1.85	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.82-1.65	3	<i>m</i>	
1.54-1.31	3	<i>m</i>		
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 144.8, 140.8, 138.7, 128.8, 128.7, 127.8, 124.2, 121.6, 60.0, 36.4, 32.8, 26.6, 26.2				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 239 (7), 211 (19), 210 (61), 183 (43), 182 (100), 168 (37), 167 (26), 154 (26), 130 (16), 127 (16), 115 (16), 89 (16)				

Chem. Name	3-(<i>p</i>-tolyl)-8<i>H</i>-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-<i>a</i>]isoindole (4f)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Tetrahedron</i> 2010 , 66, 8846–8853			
METHOD:				
Substrate 3f (1.2 mmol, 450 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (273 mg, 92% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃	m.p.	163-164 °C	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 77.71; H, 5.30; N, 16.99. Found: C, 77.67; H, 5.32; N, 16.96				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.89	1	<i>d</i>	7.2
	7.86-7.82	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.53	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	7.49-7.40	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.35-7.31	2	<i>m</i>	
	5.36	2	<i>s</i>	
	2.44	3	<i>s</i>	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 141.2, 139.5, 138.9, 138.2, 129.7, 128.9, 128.5, 128.4, 128.4, 127.0, 124.3, 121.3, 51.0, 21.5				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 247 (8), 219 (61), 218 (100), 204 (72), 189 (21), 166 (15), 109 (37), 89 (21), 63 (24)				

Chem. Name	3-((2-iodophenoxy)methyl)-8H-[1,2,3]triazolo[5,1-a]isoindole (4g)			
Lit. Ref.				
METHOD:				
Substrate 3g (1.2 mmol, 620 mg), TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 4:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was dissolved in 0.5 mL of acetone and 5 mL of cold water was added to precipitate the product. Filtration and drying gave the pure product as pale brown crystals (383 mg, 82% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ IN ₃ O	m.p.	294-296 °C (decomp.)	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 49.38; H, 3.11; N, 10.80. Found: C, 49.34; H, 3.08; N, 10.83				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.98	1	<i>d</i>	8.0
	7.75	1	<i>dd</i>	1.2, 8.0
	7.48	2	<i>t</i>	6.8
	7.42-7.38	1	<i>m</i>	
	7.28-7.24	1	<i>m</i>	
	7.07	1	<i>d</i>	7.6
	6.70	1	<i>td</i>	8.0, 1.2
	5.53	2	<i>s</i>	
5.32	2	<i>s</i>		
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 156.8, 142.0, 140.9, 139.8, 134.7, 129.7, 129.0, 128.7, 127.6, 124.0, 123.6, 123.2, 113.1, 86.5, 63.8, 51.5				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 389 (2), 319 (23), 290 (100), 235 (21), 234 (64), 221 (17), 220 (54), 204 (32), 179 (40), 130 (35), 65 (16)				

Chem. Name	Ethyl 4-(4-butyl-1-phenyl-1<i>H</i>-1,2,3-triazol-5-yl)benzoate (7a)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Chem. Commun.</i> 2016 , <i>52</i> , 9777–9780			
<p style="text-align: center;"> 5a 6b 7a </p>				
METHOD: Triazole 5a (1.2 mmol, 241 mg), 6b (3.6 mmol, 825 mg, 588 μ l) TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO ₂ H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1) to give the pure product as a colorless oil (327 mg, 78% yield).				
Mol Formula	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂		m.p.	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.18; H, 6.63; N, 12.03. Found: C, 72.15; H, 6.69; N, 11.99				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.98-7.92	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.33-7.29	3	<i>m</i>	
	7.21-7.10	4	<i>m</i>	
	4.30	2	<i>q</i>	6.8
	2.67	2	<i>t</i>	7.6
	1.67-1.58	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.34-1.22	5	<i>m</i>	
	0.80	3	<i>t</i>	7.2
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 165.89, 146.7, 136.6, 132.9, 132.2, 130.8, 129.9, 129.5, 129.3, 129.0, 124.9, 61.3, 31.7, 24.9, 22.5, 14.3, 13.8				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 349 (7), 321 (25), 279 (21), 278 (100), 175 (35), 147 (18), 104 (16), 77 (39)				

Chem. Name	Ethyl 4-(4-butyl-1-phenyl-1<i>H</i>-1,2,3-triazol-5-yl)benzoate (7a)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Chem. Commun.</i> 2016 , <i>52</i> , 9777–9780			
<p style="text-align: center;"> <chem>C1=CN=C(N1c2ccccc2)Cn3ccccc3</chem> + <chem>CCOC(=O)c1ccc(I)cc1</chem> $\xrightarrow{\text{flow reactor}}$ <chem>CCOC(=O)c1ccc(cc1)C2=C(CN=N2)c3ccccc3</chem> </p> <p style="text-align: center;"> 5a 6a 7a </p>				
METHOD:				
<p>Triazole 5a (1.2 mmol, 241 mg), 6a (3.6 mmol, 994 mg, 605 μl) TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO₂H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1) to give the pure product as a colorless oil (343 mg, 82% yield).</p>				
Mol Formula	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂		m.p.	
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.18; H, 6.63; N, 12.03. Found: C, 72.14; H, 6.67; N, 12.06				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	7.98-7.92	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.33-7.29	3	<i>m</i>	
	7.21-7.10	4	<i>m</i>	
	4.30	2	<i>q</i>	6.8
	2.67	2	<i>t</i>	7.6
	1.67-1.58	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.34-1.22	5	<i>m</i>	
	0.80	3	<i>t</i>	7.2
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 165.89, 146.7, 136.6, 132.9, 132.2, 130.8, 129.9, 129.5, 129.3, 129.0, 124.9, 61.3, 31.7, 24.9, 22.5, 14.3, 13.8				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 349 (7), 321 (25), 279 (21), 278 (100), 175 (35), 147 (18), 104 (16), 77 (39)				

Chem. Name	Ethyl 4-(4-butyl-1-(<i>p</i>-tolyl)-1<i>H</i>-1,2,3-triazol-5-yl)benzoate (7b)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Chem. Commun.</i> 2016 , <i>52</i> , 9777–9780			
METHOD:				
<p>Triazole 5b (1.2 mmol, 258 mg), 6b (3.6 mmol, 825 mg, 588 μl) TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), TBAI (1.44 mmol, 532 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO₂H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1) to give the pure product as a colorless oil (371 mg, 85% yield).</p>				
Mol Formula	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	m.p.		
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.70; H, 6.93; N, 11.56. Found: C, 72.66; H, 6.94; N, 11.52				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	8.05-7.98	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.25-7.20	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.13	4	<i>s</i>	
	4.36	2	<i>q</i>	7.2
	2.73	2	<i>t</i>	7.6
	2.33	3	<i>s</i>	
	1.75-1.65	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.39-1.30	5	<i>m</i>	
0.86	3	<i>t</i>	7.2	
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 165.89, 146.48, 139.1, 134.1, 132.9, 132.3, 130.7, 129.9, 129.8, 129.5, 124.7, 61.3, 31.7, 24.9, 22.4, 21.1, 14.3, 13.8				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 363 (2), 334 (15), 335 (48), 293 (21), 292 (100), 175 (25), 147 (16), 104 (15), 77 (41), 51 (15)				

Chem. Name	Ethyl 4-(4-butyl-1-(<i>p</i>-tolyl)-1<i>H</i>-1,2,3-triazol-5-yl)benzoate (7b)			
Lit. Ref.	<i>Chem. Commun.</i> 2016 , <i>52</i> , 9777–9780			
<p style="text-align: center;"> 5b 6a 7b </p>				
METHOD:				
<p>Triazole 5b (1.2 mmol, 258 mg), 6a (3.6 mmol, 994 mg, 605 μl) TBAAc (2.4 mmol, 723 mg), GVL (0.15M, 7.7 mL) and MesCO₂H (30 mol %, 0.36 mmol, 60 mg), were consecutively added to a reservoir tube and the resulting mixture was pumped at 0.25 mL/min through a coil reactor filled with Pd/C and thermostated at 120 °C. Reaction progress was monitored with TLC (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1). Reaction mixture was collected in a glass tube and GVL was distilled off using a Kugelrohr apparatus (0.3 mbar at 150 °C). The resulting oil was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (petroleum ether/EtOAc, 15:1) to give the pure product as a colorless oil (379 mg, 87% yield).</p>				
Mol Formula	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	m.p.		
Elemental Analysis: Calc.: C, 72.70; H, 6.93; N, 11.56. Found: C, 72.67; H, 6.89; N, 11.53				
¹H NMR 400 MHz CDCl₃	δ value	No. H	Mult.	j value/Hz
	8.05-7.98	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.25-7.20	2	<i>m</i>	
	7.13	4	<i>s</i>	
	4.36	2	<i>q</i>	7.2
	2.73	2	<i>t</i>	7.6
	2.33	3	<i>s</i>	
	1.75-1.65	2	<i>m</i>	
	1.39-1.30	5	<i>m</i>	
	0.86	3	<i>t</i>	7.2
¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 165.89, 146.48, 139.1, 134.1, 132.9, 132.3, 130.7, 129.9, 129.8, 129.5, 124.7, 61.3, 31.7, 24.9, 22.4, 21.1, 14.3, 13.8				
GC-EIMS (m/z, %): 363 (2), 334 (15), 335 (48), 293 (21), 292 (100), 175 (25), 147 (16), 104 (15), 77 (41), 51 (15)				